

DAMPING CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS BY MECHANICAL SPECTROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the application of damping capacity measurements for characterization of degradation in composite materials. Experiments were carried out with a maximum strain amplitude ϵ_M included between 10^{-6} and 3×10^{-4} . Mechanical, chemical and thermal damages were applied on various kinds of composite materials with organic or metallic matrix. Damping variation versus ϵ_M was found the main characteristic of the sample microstructural damage.

1. INTRODUCTION

The influence of damage on internal friction of composite materials under cyclic loadings was already shown by several authors [1], [2], [3], [4]. These experiments were carried out with the same progressively damaged sample at fixed frequency and damping capacity was always shown increasing with damage degree.

Such experiments do not allow to characterize directly the microstructural state of an unknown sample. Indeed composite damping capacity is strongly dependent on several parameters as making, or fibre percentage for instance. The present work shows the damping versus ϵ_M curves obtained at room temperature are more characteristic of the sample microstructural state.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Damping measurements

Results were obtained with an evacuated flexural pendulum elsewhere described [5] and allowing experiments performed at strain amplitudes included between 10^{-6} and 3×10^{-4} at fixed temperature (~ 1 Hz). Damping capacity was measured by free vibrational decay with an accuracy of 10^{-4} .

2.2. Mechanical damages

Two kinds of mechanical damages were carried out on composite samples. Very weak intensity impacts were obtained with the apparatus described in figure 1 : a hammer propelled by an electric engine taps a sample at the frequency of 1.3 Hz. The sample is a flat bar with 70 mm length, 8 mm width and 2.5 mm thickness and can be set up directly on the flexural pendulum after impact tests.

Figure 1. Sketch of the apparatus for repetitive impacts.

The influence of explosive shock waves was studied on square sheets (70 mm x 70 mm) with 4 mm thickness. The sketch of the explosive mechanism is shown in figure 2. A 130 mm – diameter copper cylinder was used as shock absorber. Various pressures on samples were obtained for different copper thickness. Explosion was set off in a tube filled with nitromethane.

Figure 2. Experiment for obtaining shock wave on composite material sheet.

After the explosion, the sheets were cut in seven internal friction samples (figure 3) numbered from 0 (high pressure) to 4 (low pressure).

Figure 3. Samples cutting out from a shocked sheet.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Moisture influence

Figure 4 shows results obtained on a composite sample with carbon fibres (60 %) in an epoxy resin matrix. Curve a was obtained after the sample was kept at 120°C during two days for complete drying. The sample was successively moistened in saturated water vapour at 80°C during a week. The sample weight increase was 2.4 %. After drying at 120°C and initial weight return, the sample was again tested on pendulum and curve b was obtained.

Figure 4. Internal friction measured on carbon-epoxy sample for dried initial state (a) and after moistening and drying (b).

As shown in figure 4, the difference between internal friction measured after (b) and before (a) moistening and drying is more and more important with ϵ_M increase. As previously indicated, measurement accuracy is 10^{-4} , while the difference between experimental curves a and b reaches 5×10^{-4} .

Identical results were obtained on a composite with 60 % aramid fibres and polypropylène matrix. Curve a on figure 5 is relative to a dry sample. After moistening at 80 % in saturated water vapor during 4 days, internal friction measurements correspond to curve b. Curve c obtained after successive drying is situated between curve a and curve b.

Figure 5. Internal friction measured on aramid - polypropylene sample.
a : dry initial state b : after moistening c : after successive drying

3.2. Impact influence

A large number of very weak impacts was applied on a carbon-epoxy sample. Internal friction experiments were carried out at the initial state, and after 100, 700 and 1000 impacts, and the obtained results are shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. Internal friction measured on carbon-epoxy sample.

1 : initial state 2 : after 100 impacts
3 : after 700 impacts 4 : after 1000 impacts

For the initial state (curve 1), the internal friction values measured for $\epsilon_M = 10^{-5}$ and for $\epsilon_M = 2 \times 10^{-4}$ were respectively 16×10^{-4} and 26×10^{-4} . So the difference ΔQ^{-1} between these two measurements is 10×10^{-4} . After 100 impacts and for the same conditions, this difference is $\Delta Q^{-1} = 14 \times 10^{-4}$. After 700 impacts and 1000 impacts, we obtain respectively $\Delta Q^{-1} = 30 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\Delta Q^{-1} = 66 \times 10^{-4}$.

For an aramid-polycarbonate composite (figure 7), the difference ΔQ^{-1} between results obtained for $\epsilon_M = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ and for $\epsilon_M = 10^{-5}$ is 85×10^{-4} for the sample at the initial state (curve 1) and 100×10^{-4} after the sample was submitted to 20 impacts (curve 2). After 300 impacts, experiments were carried out only until $\epsilon_M = 10^{-4}$, but curve 3 clearly shows the internal friction quickly increases with ϵ_M .

Figure 7. Internal friction measured on aramid-polycarbonate sample.
1 : initial state 3 : after 300 impacts 2 : after 20 impacts

3.3. Shock wave influence

Three explosive experiments were carried out on carbon-epoxy sheets with different pressures at the centre of the sheet : 20, 30 and 40 kbar obtained for various absorber thicknesses. Figure 8 shows that internal friction of sample 1 (see figure 3) for each sheet, gradually increase for higher pressure.

Figure 8. Internal friction measured on samples 1 cut out sheets submitted to different explosive pressures.

a : sample reference b : 20 kbar c : 30 kbar d : 40 kbar.

Identical result is shown in figure 9. Curves b, c and d correspond to samples 2, 1 and 0 respectively cut out the sheet submitted to a 40 kbar-explosive pressure. Curve a corresponds to a reference sample without damage. Sample 0 was strongly delaminated and exhibits a very high damping.

Figure 9. Internal friction measured on samples cut out a sheet submitted to explosive pressure (40 kbar).

a : sample reference b : sample 2 c : sample 1 d : sample 0

3.4. Thermal treatment influence

Influence of high temperature annealings was studied on a metal matrix composite with 20 % SiC whiskers and 2024 – aluminium alloy matrix. Experiments were carried out at room temperature after increasing temperature annealings. Results are shown in figure 10.

For the initial state (curve a), internal friction is constant for ϵ_M included from 2×10^{-4} to 3×10^{-3} . On the contrary, damping depends on ϵ_M after high temperature annealing : weakly after annealing at 145°C (curve b) and more and more strongly after annealings at 300°C (curve c), 420°C (curve d) and 550°C (curve e). It can be noted than for low amplitude measurements (until $\epsilon_M = 5 \times 10^{-4}$), internal friction is nearly independent with temperature annealing. Difference between different curves is observed only above $\epsilon_M = 10^{-3}$.

Figure 10. Internal friction measured at room temperature on a 2024 - aluminium alloy matrix composite at the initial state (a) and after annealings at 145°C (b), 300°C (c), 420°C (d) and 550°C (e).

4. DISCUSSION - CONCLUSION

All these experiments clearly show that the damping measured in function of the maximum strain amplitude ϵ_M is strongly dependent on the sample state. For sample without damage Q^{-1} versus ϵ_M curves are nearly flat. On the contrary, for damaged samples, damping is more and more dependent on ϵ_M . Therefore the main damping characteristic for a composite sample is the difference between Q^{-1} measured for high ϵ_M and Q^{-1} for low ϵ_M . After mechanical damages, the damping increasing is probably due to a large number of small cracks in matrix or fibre breaking. Whaley [6] described a mathematical model for internal friction after fatigue damage based on population of yielding microelements. According to the model, Q^{-1} increases with ϵ_M , exactly like our experiments after smaller mechanical damages.

For moistened samples, the damping modification can rather be connected with alteration in organic matrix or in the matrix-fibre interface.

At last, the modification of the dislocation microstructure during high temperature annealings can explain the results obtained on the metal matrix composite.

References

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